

Impact of Zn/Cr Ratio on ZnCrO_x-SAPO-34 Bifunctional Catalyst for Direct Conversion of Syngas to Light Olefins

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Abstract—Light olefins are important building blocks for chemical industry. Direct conversion of syngas to light olefins has been investigated for decades. Meanwhile, the limit for light olefins selectivity described by Anderson-Schulz-Flory (ASF) distribution model is still a great challenge to conventional Fischer-Tropsch synthesis. The emerging strategy called oxide-zeolite concept (OX-ZEO) is a promising way to get rid of this limit. ZnCrO_x was prepared by co-precipitation method and (NH₄)₂CO₃ was used as precipitant. SAPO-34 was prepared by hydrothermal synthesis, and Tetraethylammonium hydroxide (TEAOH) was used as template, while silica sol, pseudo-boehmite, and phosphoric acid were Al, Si and P source, respectively. The bifunctional catalyst was prepared by mechanical mixing of ZnCrO_x and SAPO-34. Catalytic reactions were carried out under H₂/CO=2, 380 °C, 1 MPa and 6000 mL·g_{cat}⁻¹·h⁻¹ in a fixed-bed reactor with a quartz lining. Catalysts were characterized by XRD, N₂ adsorption-desorption, NH₃-TPD, H₂-TPR, and CO-TPD. The addition of Al as structure promoter enhances CO conversion and selectivity to light olefins. Zn/Cr ratio, which decides the active component content and chemisorption property of the catalyst, influences CO conversion and selectivity to light olefins at the same time. C₂₋₄ distribution of 86% among hydrocarbons at CO conversion of 14% was reached when Zn/Cr=1.5.

Keywords—Light olefins, OX-ZEO, syngas, ZnCrO_x.

I. INTRODUCTION

LIGHT olefins, consisting of ethylene, propylene, and butylene, are key chemicals. At present light olefins are mainly gained from naphtha cracking [1]. Syngas, a mixture of CO and H₂, is a vital platform for chemicals production via nonpetroleum route. Indirect conversion of syngas to light olefins has been industrialized, composing of methanol production and MTO (methanol-to-olefins) process. Meanwhile, Fischer-Tropsch (F-T) synthesis, which is the major path of syngas to light olefins, has been investigated for over 90 years [2]-[4]. However, the hydrocarbon distribution is still a challenge to its commercialization, as the ASF model shows that the carbon-based selectivity of light olefins is limited to less than 60%.

Recently, a strategy called OX-ZEO process was raised up with a high light olefins selectivity and little methane was formed [5]. According to the OX-ZEO process, CO and H₂ are

activated over the partially reduced metal oxide, leading to the formation of CH₄ and intermediate. Subsequently, the intermediate participates the C-C coupling, which is controlled by zeolite pores with acidic sites. The nature of intermediate is still a matter of debate. Some authors pointed out that methanol or dimethyl ether is the intermediate [6], [7], which means the OX-ZEO process can be understood as the combination of methanol production and MTO process. Other authors proposed that ketene is the intermediate [5], [8].

Different oxides have been investigated, such as ZnCrO_x, ZnO-ZrO₂, ZnGa₂O₄, and MnO_x [5], [7], [9], [10]. ZnCrO_x is used to produce light olefins and other organic products with different kinds of zeolite via OX-ZEO process, but the Zn/Cr ratio and its impact to catalytic performance has never been discussed [8], [11], [12]. Herein, we prepared ZnCrO_x with different Zn/Cr ratio and investigated the impact of Zn/Cr ratio on the catalytic performance of bifunctional catalyst for direct conversion of syngas to light olefins. The addition of Al was also discussed.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

A. Catalyst Preparation

ZnCrO_x oxide was prepared by coprecipitation method. Briefly, 22.31 g Zn(NO₃)₂·6H₂O and 20.01g Cr(NO₃)₃·9H₂O were dissolved in 125 mL deionized water and heated to 70 °C. The solution was added to (NH₄)₂CO₃ solution under 70 °C until the pH value of the suspension arrived 7.0. The suspension was aged for 3h under 70 °C, followed by centrifugation and washed with deionized water to neutral. The resulting product was dried under 110 °C for 12h and calcined under 500 °C for 1h under static air. The catalyst was denoted as Zn-Cr-1.5-1, which means the molar ratio of Zn/Cr atom is 1.5:1. The catalyst containing Al was denoted as Zn-Cr-Al-3.5-1-1, which means the molar ratio of Zn/Cr/Al atom is 3.5:1:1.

SAPO-34 was synthesized hydrothermally [13]. 85% H₃PO₄ and 35% TEAOH was added to deionized water under continuous stirring. Subsequently, 30% silica sol was added dropwise into the solution, followed by addition of aluminium isopropoxide in small quantity. After vigorous stirring for 1h, 35% hydrochloric acid was added dropwise. The mixture was transferred into a 200-mL Teflon-lined stainless steel autoclave after intense stirring for 1 h. The hydrothermal synthesis proceeded under 190 °C for 32h with rotation. After centrifugation and washing, the solid product was dried under 110 °C for 12h and calcined under 550 °C for 3h under flowing

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air.

B. Catalytic Performance Test

Catalytic reactions were performed in a fixed-bed stainless steel reactor with a quartz lining. ZnCrO_x oxide and SAPO-34 were both dried by a far-infrared dryer before being weighed. 150 mg ZnCrO_x oxide (250-425 μm) and SAPO-34 with same weight and size were mixed in a centrifuge tube. After vigorous shaking, 300-mg composite catalyst was sent into the reactor. The composite catalyst was reduced in situ in H₂ under 310 °C for 3 h. Catalytic reaction was carried out under 380 °C, 1MPa, H₂/CO/N₂=60/30/10 and GHSV=6000 mL·g_{cat}⁻¹·h⁻¹. Products were analyzed by an online Agilent 7890A GC. The catalytic performance after 800 minutes of reaction was used for discussion. The carbon balance was over 99%. The calculation of CO conversion was below.

$$X_{CO} = \frac{CO_{in} - CO_{out}}{CO_{in}} \times 100\%$$

where CO_{in} and CO_{out} represent molar flow of CO at the inlet and outlet, respectively.

The calculations of selectivity to CO₂ and hydrocarbons were below.

$$S_{CO_2} = \frac{CO_{2,out}}{CO_{in} - CO_{out}} \times 100\%$$

where CO_{2,out} represents molar flow of CO₂ at the outlet.

$$S_{C_nH_m} = \frac{nC_nH_{m,out}}{\sum nC_nH_{m,out}} \times 100\%$$

where C_nH_m represents molar flow of C_nH_m at the outlet.

C. Characterization

XRD was performed on a Bruker D8 Advance X-ray polycrystalline diffractometer with Cu Kα radiation at 40 kV and 40 mA in the range of 2θ=5-80°.

N₂ adsorption-desorption was carried out at -196 °C on a micromeritics ASAP 2020. All samples were degassed under vacuum at 350 °C for 6h before analysis. The micropore volume was calculated by t-plot method.

NH₃-TPD was carried out on a micromeritics AutoChem II 2920. 0.1 g sample was pretreated in flowing He at 600 °C for 30 minutes. After cooling down to 60 °C under flowing He, the adsorption of 10%NH₃ in He was proceeded under 60 °C for 30 minutes. Then, He flow was used to purge excess NH₃ for 30 minutes until a stable baseline was obtained. At last, signal was recorded when the temperature was increased from 60 °C to 800 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min under flowing He.

H₂-TPR was carried out on a micromeritics AutoChem II 2920. 0.05 g sample was pretreated in flowing Ar at 400 °C for 60 minutes. After cooling down to 60 °C under flowing Ar until

a stable baseline was obtained, 10%H₂ in Ar was used to proceed reduction. Signal was recorded when the temperature was increased from 60 °C to 800 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min under flowing Ar.

CO-TPD was carried out on a micromeritics AutoChem II 2920. At first, 0.25g sample underwent in situ reduction with H₂ at 310 °C for 3 hours. After cooling down to 60 °C under flowing He, the adsorption of carbon monoxide was proceeded under 60 °C for 30 minutes. Then, He flow was used to purge excess CO for 30 minutes until a stable baseline was obtained. At last, signal was recorded when the temperature was increased from 60 °C to 800 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min under flowing He.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. XRD

XRD patterns showed that Zn-Cr-0.5-1 was composed of pure ZnCr₂O₄ spinel structure since the characteristic peaks of ZnO were negligible (Fig. 1 (b)). Zn-Cr-1.5-1 to Zn-Cr-4.5-1 were composed of ZnCr₂O₄ and ZnO. The addition of Zn introduced ZnO, and ZnO became dominant along with the addition of Zn. The addition of Al to Zn-Cr-3.5-1 widened the peak, which indicated that Al can decrease the particle size as structure promoter. Meanwhile, neither ZnAl₂O₄ nor Al₂O₃ was observed on the XRD pattern of Zn-Cr-Al-3.5-1-1, which might be due to the low content of Al.

XRD pattern of SAPO-34 was shown in Fig. 2. The synthesized SAPO-34 exhibited the typical XRD patterns of zeolites with the chabazite (CHA) framework topology.

B. Catalytic Performance

Considering the XRD result and catalytic performance, the metal oxide samples can be divided into ZnCrAlO_x (Zn-Cr-Al-3.5-1-1) and ZnCrO_x, and ZnCrO_x can be divided into ZnCr₂O₄ (Zn-Cr-0.5-1) and ZnO-ZnCr₂O₄ (Zn-Cr-1.5-1 to Zn-Cr-4.5-1). Fig. 3 showed the catalytic performance of bifunctional catalyst for direct conversion of syngas to light olefins. From the comparison between Zn-Cr-0.5-1 and Zn-Cr-1.5-1, it can be concluded that the addition of ZnO to ZnCr₂O₄ can significantly increase the CO conversion, while CH₄ selectivity decreased and light olefins selectivity increased obviously. The olefins/paraffins ratio also increased.

As the Zn/Cr ratio increased in ZnO-ZnCr₂O₄, CO conversion decreased slightly, while CH₄ and C₅₊ selectivity increased, and light olefins selectivity decreased slightly as well. However, the olefins/paraffins ratio decreased obviously.

The addition of Al to Zn-Cr-3.5-1 led to a noteworthy increase to CO conversion. CH₄ and C₅₊ selectivity decreased, while both light olefins selectivity and olefins/paraffins ratio increased.

On the basis of these data, it can be concluded that there exists an optimal Zn/Cr ratio for bifunctional catalyst. Among the samples that we have prepared, the best Zn/Cr ratio is 1.5. 14% CO conversion, 3.9% CH₄ and 85.68% light olefins among hydrocarbons were achieved under 380 °C, 1 MPa, H₂/CO=2, GHSV=6000 mL·g_{cat}⁻¹·h⁻¹, TOS=800 min.

Furthermore, the addition of Al promotes the catalytic performance notably. Details will be discussed below with

NH_3 -TPD, N_2 adsorption-desorption, H_2 -TPR, and CO-TPD.

Fig. 1 XRD patterns of metal oxides (a) $2\theta=25-75^\circ$ (b) $2\theta=28-38^\circ$

Fig. 2 XRD pattern of the synthesized SAPO-34

C. NH_3 -TPD

NH_3 -TPD profile showed the acid property of the synthesized SAPO-34 (Fig. 3). The peak at the lower temperature (137 °C in this case) has been proven to be related to a weakly held ammonia, which may be adsorbed by hydrogen bond, but not the ammonia species adsorbed on the acid site. The peak at the higher temperature (347 °C in this case) is widely used to characterize strong acid site in zeolite [14], [15]. Compared with the literature [5], SAPO-34 that we

have synthesized exhibited a rather weak strong acid. Therefore, the hydrogen transfer reaction was suppressed, leading to the high light olefins selectivity among most of the catalytic performance tests.

Since all the catalytic performance tests used the same SAPO-34, the difference of $\text{C}_{2-4}^-/\text{C}_{2-4}^0$ among the results should not be ascribed to the acid property of SAPO-34.

D. N_2 Adsorption-Desorption

The textural properties of metal oxides and SAPO-34 were shown in Table I. BET surface area of ZnCrO_x became slightly smaller along with the addition of Zn, but the difference is insignificant. The pore volume was similar among ZnCrO_x with varying Zn/Cr ratio. Hence, the impact of Zn/Cr ratio on the textural properties of catalysts should not be a key factor to the difference in catalytic performance. However, CO conversion increased from 12.81% to 15.99% as the addition of Al doubled BET surface area and pore volume. The impact of Al was noteworthy. Al played the role of structure promoter and increased the surface area of metal oxide, leading to more ZnCr_2O_4 being exposed to the surface rather than in bulk phase. It directly increased active sites for CO activation and influenced the chemisorption property.

Fig. 3 Catalytic performance of bifunctional catalysts (a) CO conversion, CH₄ selectivity and C₅₊ selectivity (b) Light olefins selectivity and Olefins/paraffins ratio of C₂₋₄ hydrocarbon

Fig. 4 NH₃-TPD pattern of the synthesized SAPO-34

TABLE I
TEXTURAL PROPERTIES FOR METAL OXIDES AND SAPO-34

Sample	BET Surface Area (m ² /g)	V _{total} (cm ³ /g)	V _{micro} (cm ³ /g)	V _{meso} /V _{total} (%)
Zn-Cr-0.5-1	66.77	0.25	0.00	100
Zn-Cr-1.5-1	65.85	0.30	0.00	100
Zn-Cr-2.5-1	62.29	0.28	0.00	100
Zn-Cr-3.5-1	60.27	0.27	0.00	100
Zn-Cr-4.5-1	57.41	0.27	0.00	100
Zn-Cr-Al-3.5-1-1	120.66	0.54	0.00	100
SAPO-34	487.59	0.44	0.23	47.15

The synthesized SAPO-34 exhibited hierarchical pore structure, which is a benefit to achieve higher reaction activity and more resistive to carbon deposition compared with conventional SAPO-34. Combined with the rather weak strong acid and moderate acid amount of zeolite and the optimized

metal oxide, CO conversion was much higher than other reports under similar reaction condition [6], [7].

Fig. 5 H₂-TPR patterns of the metal oxides (a) Zn-Cr-0.5-1 and Zn-Cr-1.5-1 (b) Zn-Cr-1.5-1 to Zn-Cr-4.5-1 (c) Zn-Cr-3.5-1 and Zn-Cr-Al-3.5-1-1

E. H₂-TPR

During the reduction process, several oxygen vacancies were generated on the surface of ZnCr₂O₄ spinel, and such surface

with oxygen vacancies was the site for CO activation [5]. The peak temperature for Zn-Cr-0.5-1 was much lower than Zn-Cr-1.5-1 (Fig. 5 (a)), which meant that the addition of ZnO hindered the reduction of ZnCr₂O₄, but the chosen temperature (310 °C) for H₂ reduction before the catalytic performance tests was capable of completing the reduction. The peaks for ZnO-ZnCr₂O₄ were sharper than the peak for pure ZnCr₂O₄ spinel, which indicated that ZnO facilitated to uniform the reductibility of ZnCr₂O₄. ZnO-ZnCr₂O₄ with different Zn/Cr ratio showed similar peak temperature and distribution (Fig. 5 (b)), indicating the similar reduction behavior among these samples. From the quantitative analysis listed in Table II, H₂ consumption decreased along with the addition of ZnO, owing to the mass fraction of ZnO, which is unreducible by H₂, increased. To subtract dilution effect caused by ZnO, H₂ consumption based on ZnCr₂O₄ was calculated, and H₂ consumption based on ZnCr₂O₄ increased along with the addition of ZnO, suggesting that ZnO facilitated to make full use of ZnCr₂O₄ despite that ZnO-ZnCr₂O₄ was slightly harder to be reduced than pure ZnCr₂O₄ spinel and ZnO decreased ZnCr₂O₄ mass fraction. Hence, there should be an optimal ZnO content. Zn-Cr-1.5-1 showed the highest H₂ consumption and a rather high H₂ consumption based on ZnCr₂O₄, and it showed the best catalytic performance.

The addition of Al to Zn-Cr-3.5-1 increased H₂ consumption and decreased peak temperature at the same time (Fig. 5 (c)), which can be related to the rise of surface area and pore volume. The improvement of reduction behavior also resulted in the better catalytic performance.

TABLE II
QUANTITATIVE RESULTS OF H₂-TPR

Sample	H ₂ consumption (mmol/g)	ZnCr ₂ O ₄ mass fraction	H ₂ consumption (mmol/g ZnCr ₂ O ₄)
Zn-Cr-0.5-1	0.57	1.00	0.57
Zn-Cr-1.5-1	0.78	0.59	1.33
Zn-Cr-2.5-1	0.61	0.42	1.47
Zn-Cr-3.5-1	0.53	0.32	1.64
Zn-Cr-4.5-1	0.45	0.26	1.71
Zn-Cr-Al-3.5-1-1	0.63	0.25	2.23

F. CO-TPD

Since ZnCr₂O₄ surface with oxygen vacancies is the site for CO activation, CO-TPD after in situ H₂ reduction was carried out to investigate CO adsorption behavior. Fig. 6 (a) showed the CO-TPD profiles between Zn-Cr-0.5-1 and Zn-Cr-1.5-1. The desorption peak temperature was similar at the range of lower than 300 °C. But, the decline of the peak temperature at high temperature range revealed that the interaction between CO and ZnCr₂O₄ surface with oxygen vacancies was weakened with the addition of ZnO. The textural properties of Zn-Cr-0.5-1 and Zn-Cr-1.5-1 were similar, so the difference in CO desorption was not caused by textural property. Solo ZnO had a desorption peak at 477 °C, but the amount of CO adsorption on ZnO is negligible. Therefore, the difference in CO desorption was not caused by CO adsorption on ZnO.

Fig. 6 CO-TPD patterns of the metal oxides (a) Zn-Cr-0.5-1 and Zn-Cr-1.5-1 (b) Zn-Cr-1.5-1 to Zn-Cr-4.5-1 (c) Zn-Cr-3.5-1 and Zn-Cr-Al-3.5-1-1

Recently, a DFT research [16] that focused on excess Zn on spinel-structured ZnCr_2O_4 showed that the adsorption of CO on ZnCr_2O_4 with excess Zn is weaker than on stoichiometric ZnCr_2O_4 , indicating higher reactivity. The structure was reported to be a thin, amorphous ZnO layer supported on the ZnCr_2O_4 spinel. At the higher concentration of incorporated Zn,

the oxygen vacancy formation energy decreases, indicating high reducibility of the system. Our experimental results of CO-TPD were in accord with this literature.

CO-TPD profiles among $\text{ZnO-ZnCr}_2\text{O}_4$ with different Zn/Cr ratio were similar (Fig. 6 (b)), since both the textural structure the surface composition [16] were similar. Fig. 6 (c) showed that the addition of Al had no effect on peak temperature, but increased the amount of CO adsorption, owing to the improvement of textural property. The increased surface area exposed more ZnCr_2O_4 to the surface without changing its chemical environment, thus provided more oxygen vacancies to adsorb CO.

IV. CONCLUSION

A series of Zn-Cr oxides were prepared by coprecipitation and were mixed with SAPO-34 to be used as bifunctional catalyst for direct conversion of syngas to light olefins. The Zn/Cr ratio was found to be a critical factor on the catalytic property, whereas the presence of Al had a crucial influence on the textural and catalytic property. The ideal Zn/Cr ratio among the samples that we prepared was 1.5. It exhibited CO conversion of 14%, light olefins selectivity of 86% when mixed with SAPO-34, while CH_4 selectivity was only 3.9%. ZnCr_2O_4 and $\text{ZnO-ZnCr}_2\text{O}_4$ showed similar textural property but exhibited different catalytic performances when mixed with SAPO-34. H_2 -TPR revealed that ZnO facilitated the reduction of ZnCr_2O_4 , but too much addition of ZnO decreased the portion of ZnCr_2O_4 . CO-TPD indicated that ZnO significantly weakened the interaction between the adsorbed CO and the surface with oxygen vacancy, which is consistent with the calculation from literature [16]. Zn-Cr-Al-3.5-1-1 exhibited CO conversion of 16%, light olefins selectivity of 84% when mixed with SAPO-34, while CH_4 selectivity was only 3.5%. The addition of Al to $\text{ZnO-ZnCr}_2\text{O}_4$ did not change the phase components, but improved the textural property, leading to the enhancement of reducibility and chemisorption property to CO, which resulted in a better catalytic performance.

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